

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Dissemination Plan

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	PP	Restricted to other project participants (including R4D services)	
	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D services)	
	CO	Confidential, only for project and the R4D services	
Status	to be continuously updated		

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1 Executive summary

This document contains the dissemination plan and it refers to the process of making the results and deliverables of a project available to stakeholders and a wider audience. Dissemination is essential for take-up, and take-up is crucial for the success of a project and for the sustainability of outputs in the long term view.

The goal of this document is to provide a dedicated plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication of project activities and results. All these are issues addressed within the work package (WP) 1: "*Dissemination, exploitation and communication*". This WP remains led by SUPSI. All team members will have to perform dedicated dissemination activities at country level and eventually abroad. This document aims at being up-to-date and actually useful. To meet this goal, we aim to be community edited. Whenever you discover flaws or potential improvements, please discuss your proposal by writing an email to the Project Coordinator. The Project Coordinator (SUPSI) will promote the dissemination activities and all partners will actively contribute.

2 Dissemination strategy

The dissemination strategy follows principles and best practices already successfully tested in other projects carried out by most of the project partners. All research results will be reviewed and a copy will be sent to relevant policy partners involved in the project before these are published or disseminated. All people who contribute to the project activities, for example by taking part in public surveys or expert interviews, will be duly informed about the final outcomes and the implications stemming from project results.

3 Dissemination activities, tools, timing and responsibilities

The main objective of dissemination remains to raise awareness among stakeholders about the project objectives and to disseminate relevant and appropriate information. This should ensure the maximum exploitation of project results. All stakeholders have to be informed about improvements and news concerning the development of the 4onse project. Outside the 4onse environment, also other communities have to be informed about the ongoing project developments.

The presented dissemination strategy covers the following topics:

1. Objectives of dissemination
2. Target groups of dissemination

3. Methods and tools
4. Time schedule of activities
5. Responsibilities

In the following chapters, these points are described in detail.

3.1 Objectives of dissemination

The dissemination and exploitation plan will be implemented to provide information, receive feedback and engage in dialogue with the relevant stakeholders involved in project activities and also with outstanding communities or entities. The final goal of dissemination is to see the 4nse monitoring system widely known and hopefully implemented in countries where financial resources of investments for observing the environment are limited.

For the target group of decision-makers and policy implementers, the main objective is to influence their attitude to deal with the monitoring system implementation and to convince them applying the proposed 4nse solutions. For other target groups the goal stays in creating interest in the system solution, launch a contact or collaboration with one or more of the project partners.

3.2 Target groups of dissemination

The proposed plan is based on the target groups shown in table 1, which have different features and require different dissemination approaches.

Target group	Entity type
Decision makers and policy implementers (local and regional governmental decision makers)	Public (countrywide)
Stakeholders from the productive sector (water utilities, industry of goods, agro-food industry, farmers associations)	Private (countrywide)
Stakeholders from the water service sector (water utilities, geo-engineering companies, irrigation sector)	Public/private (countrywide)
Scientific world	Public

(universities and research centers both public and private)	(worldwide)
Nonscientific world (associations for the protection of the environment, the general public, etc...)	Public (worldwide)

Table 1: Identified target groups

At the current stage, about 15 decision makers, policy implementers and stakeholders from the productive sector from the partner country Sri Lanka are involved. Most of them belong to public ministries (Irrigation Department, Central Environmental Authority, Rice research and Development institute, National Building Research Organization etc.). During the next months, all the other target groups mentioned in table 1 will be involved, using methods described in the next chapter.

3.3 Methods and tools

Dissemination and exploitation activities will take place through different means and will be organized in several tasks. Table 2 presents a list of dissemination and exploitations means that will be used to target specific groups, with distinction between interpersonal and mass media communication.

Interpersonal communication	Media communication
Interpersonal communication	Technical or scientific papers
Group discussions	Newsletters
Conferences	Brochures, booklets, flyers
Brokerage events	Emails
Meetings, round tables	Video

Exhibitions	Posters
Dissemination workshops	Website
Demonstrations	Blogs
Phone calls	Radio, TV

Table 2: List of dissemination and exploitation means

Interpersonal Communication is based on the physical contact between different stakeholders and several target groups, through individual meetings and participation in events, allowing more personal and stronger links to be established. This kind of relationship is mandatory for influencing key target groups.

The WP 1 leader must be aware of meetings and participation in events. Information and outcomes must be communicated to the rest of the project partners to ensure proper coordination of the dissemination activities. It is necessary to develop a contact database and to create a map of contacts to avoid lack of coordination in action with people and entities external to the team.

Among all the dissemination means, internet based tools constitute main channel for disseminating the project information. They allow many target groups to be reached at once. It also allows for dissemination to be carried out on an ongoing basis and for information to be always available to stakeholders. The professional public will be reached through the professional media, making it a powerful means of creating awareness of the existence, progress and results of the entire project.

In Table 3 the foreseen dissemination tools are envisaged. Most of them are already available to the 4nse team and the outside world. If new useful dissemination tools are identified during the project, they will be added to and properly documented in this document.

Project Identity	Internet tools	Events and promotional activities	Publications
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Logo	Website	Project events/meetings	Technical/scientific papers
Acronym	Partner websites	Conferences, seminars	Newsletters
Banners	Cloud (restricted access)	Training and workshops	TV, Radio
Presentations	LinkedIn		
Posters	Twitter		
Brochures/Booklet	Agenda (public)		

Table 3: Dissemination tools

3.4 Time schedule of activities

The dissemination activities will be executed during the whole project duration of 30 months and started already at the Kick-off date. Up to now, several activities have been completed and the deliverables (Dn.n) have been provided:

- the target stakeholders list contains 15 entities from Sri Lanka, other target groups are under investigation (D1.2).
- the project identity has been established and the corresponding manual delivered (D1.3).
- Dissemination interim reports (D1.5) will be delivered every 12 months, first edition in September 2017.

3.5 Responsibilities

The lead partner for the dissemination WP1 is SUPSI, meanwhile all partners will make use of their networks and contacts in their country/region. All these information are delivered to the communication manager who is in charge to transfer these information to one or several communication platforms (internet tools).

4 Resources and budget

Each project partner has the obligation to provide resources to obtain the above mentioned objectives. This includes manpower and, if required, also occurring financial resources. The lead partner SUPSI provides the infrastructure of the website, which includes the costs of maintenance of the server (hosted at SUPSI, Institute of Earth Science) and the updates of the website. Also the maintenance of the other internet tools (Twitter, LinkedIn, etc.) is provided by SUPSI.

5 Evaluation criteria and dissemination assessment

An *effective* dissemination is essential in order to ensure that research results are adapted for the specific target groups. An important step is to identify measurable criteria to evaluate the dissemination strategy. On the other hand, not all possible criteria are objectively measurable. Table 4 summarizes the different dissemination mechanisms along with their measurable criteria of success. These criteria will be monitored during the whole project duration to assess the dissemination strategy and, if necessary, to modify it. Hereby the effort of all project partners is required.

Dissemination tools	Criteria of success
Internet tools	Number of visitors, page views, new/returning visitors, number of downloads, number of comments, number of tweets
Project events/meetings	Number of participants, media interest, collected feedback
Conferences, seminars	Number of participants, number of participating countries, media interest, collected feedback
Training and workshops	Number of participants, number of participating countries, collected feedback

Press, TV, Radio	Frequency of appearance, collected feedback
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Table 4: criteria of success